

bands with their extinction coefficients being 25 and 35. In the case of base adducts only one absorption band is observed around 680-700 nm region very near to the second band of the mixed chelates. Eventhough, the position of this band has not changed much in the base adducts, the intensity of the band is relatively higher. A clear isobestic point and high extinction coefficient value indicate that only two species are involved. With increased amounts of base being added, the intensity goes up but the position of band maxima does not change appreciably. In the case of bis-adduct (compd. 6) the intensity value is quite high. It was observed¹⁴⁻¹⁷ that in the case of base adducts, the extinction coefficient values increase without much shifting of the band maxima. Our observations are similar to those mentioned above. Therefore, it appears that all the adducts are presumably penta-coordinated mono-adducts of the mixed chelates except the adduct of (hfac) which is a six-coordinated bis-adduct. Formation of the mixed chelates reveals the lability of the β -diketonate moiety.

The enhanced stability of the base adducts of mixed chelates is due to the increasing Lewis acid character of the chelates as a result of the replacement of one of the acetylacetonato group by a β -diketonate having electron withdrawing substituents.

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Reactions of 2,4-Pentanedionato Complexes Bromination of Tris(2,4-pentanedionato) iron(III)

N. H. PAIKE

Department of Chemistry,
Shri Sharanabasaveshwar College of Science,
Karnataka-585 103

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AN extensive work has been reported¹⁻⁵ on the physico-chemical properties of tris(2,4-pentanedionato)iron(III), $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$. The bromination reactions of $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$ suggested^{6,7} that the reaction conditions have a deciding effect on the nature of the reaction products. This view was also supported from the reaction of powdered solid $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$, with liquid bromine⁸. The reaction resulted in the oxidative decomposition of the complex, producing $\text{Ni}^{\text{III}} \text{Br}_3$ which was confirmed by a number of observations. This gave the initiation to carry out the bromination reaction of $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ in a similar manner. Some interesting observations and findings on the reaction of $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ with liquid bromine and reactions of brominated product with various ligands have been elucidated in this paper.

Experimental

Tris(2,4-pentanedionato)iron(III) was synthesised and purified by the reported method⁹. Finely powdered tris(2,4-pentanedionato)iron(III) (0.3 mol) was treated with liquid bromine (3 mol). The reaction was allowed to complete at room temperature in dry atmosphere. After the completion of the reaction, unreacted bromine was removed by repeated washings with n-heptane. The removal of unreacted bromine was tested with aqueous potassium iodide solution (10%). The brominated product was dark red at room temperature, vacuum dried and solidified in dry-ice.

The elemental analyses of C and H were done at Micro Analytical Division of the Chemistry Department, University of Poona. Measurements of the electrical conductivity were carried out on Philips GM 4144 conductivity bridge. The half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) of the reaction product were made on the polarographic instrument at the Central Electro Chemical Research Institute, Karaikudi. Electronic spectra were recorded in solution on Beckman DB spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities of the brominated product were measured from 100 K to room temperature on Gouy type balance at the Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay. The epr spectra were recorded on standard Varian E-4 instrument and at Indian Institute of Technology, Madras.

Results and Discussion

A dark red viscous mass was obtained when finely powdered $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ was allowed to react with liquid bromine. The product of the reaction was a

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF BROMINATED PRODUCT

Compound	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				Colour	Solubility
		Fe	C	H	Br		
Fe(acac) ₃	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₆ Fe	15.63	50.80	6.32	—	Orange	Common organic solvents Acetonitrile, nitrobenzene, acetone
Fe(HacacBr)Br(Br ₃) ₂	C ₇ H ₇ O ₂ Br ₃ Fe	6.78 (6.82)	10.21 (10.26)	— (0.85)	68.15 (68.39)	Dark red	

semisolid and could be solidified in dry-ice (-70°). The red reaction product was investigated in acetonitrile solvent by the polarographic technique using lithium perchlorate as a supporting electrolyte. The result showed two irreversible waves.

These values are in excellent agreement with the reported ones¹⁰. Tris(2,4-pentanedionato)iron(III), its brominated product and derivatives were subjected to elemental analysis (Table 1). On the basis of analysis the formula of the product was assigned to be Fe(HacacBr)Br₇. The bromine analysis by the iodometric and silver nitrate method is suggestive of the presence of two tribromide ionic species of the product. The product exhibits solution conductivity tending towards 1 : 2 electrolyte behaviour in both the solvents at room temperature¹¹ (Table 2).

The equilibrium constant for the ionization in acetonitrile was calculated¹² to be 4.5×10^{-3} on the basis of 1 : 1 electrolytic nature. The conductivity

TABLE 2—SOLUTION CONDUCTIVITY DATA

Solvent	0.01 M	0.005 M	0.0025 M	Δ_{∞}
	Λ	$\Omega^{-1} \text{ l}^{-1} \text{ M}^{-1}$		Ω^{-1}
Acetone	116.9	124.6	131.9	151.8
Acetonitrile	131.8	141.5	154.6	186.2

measurements showed that the reaction product is nearing 1 : 2 electrolytic nature. If the same assumption is extended towards the extraction method of calculating the equilibrium constant, then the equilibrium process would be formulated as

The equilibrium constant (Table 3) has been calculated on this formulation. It appears appropriate to call this equilibrium constant k_1 than the overall equilibrium constant as the reaction was assumed to be the decomposition of only one tribromide ion. From the reaction product it appears that to be similar to one of the few complexes of transition metals containing trihalide ion¹³.

TABLE 3—DATA ON EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT

Temp. °C	pK conductometry	pK extraction	pK, for (teab + Br) ₂ voltammetry*
	25	2.35	6.87

* I. V. Nelson and T. R. Iwamoto, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 218.

The interesting features of the product are, (i) the presence of neutral 3-bromo-2,4-pentanedione in the complex, and (ii) the presence of two Br₃⁻ and one Br⁻ as coordinating ions.

The electronic spectrum (Fig. 1) of the reaction product support the presence of the tribromide ion, and HacacBr in it. The electronic spectral assignments (Table 4) and the positions of the reaction product conform to an octahedral high spin iron(III) ion, similar to those reported in the literature for high spin iron(III) compounds. The high spin nature of the product is evidenced from the magnet c susceptibility measurements.

Fig. 1

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF Fe(HacacBr)Br(Br₃)₂ (cm⁻¹)

Solvent	ν_1 ${}^4T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$	ν_2 ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$	ν_3 ${}^4A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^6E_g \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$
	Acetonitrile	21645	23996
Acetone	21645	23996	25907
Nitrobenzene	21505	23256	23696

The transitions due to tribromide ion were observed at 25840 and 35971 cm^{-1} and those due to the HacacBr at 31446 and 45454 cm^{-1} .

Magnetic behaviour (Table 5) of iron(III) (high spin) is quite similar to that of manganese(II). The complex shows constant magnetic moment of 5.9 ± 0.1 B.M. in the temperature range 100-300 K. Which corresponds to five unpaired electrons of the high spin iron(III).

TABLE 5—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF $\text{Fe}(\text{HacacBr})\text{Br}(\text{Br}_3)_2$

Temp. K	$\chi M \times 10^6$ mol observed	$\chi M \times 10^6$ mol observed	μ_{eff} observed B.M.
100	42170	44936	5.80
150	28300	29957	5.80
165	27200	27234	5.99
176	24800	25532	5.90
188	24200	23902	6.08
200	22150	22468	5.95
240	18500	18723	5.94
260	17000	17283	5.94
280	16230	16048	6.02
300	14665	14979	5.98

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Formation Constant and Thermodynamic Functions of Some Trivalent Rare Earth Metal Complexes of *p*-Sulpho-salicylidenesulphanilamide

G. P. SENGUPTA and C. R. BERA

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan-731 235

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LITERATURE survey reveals that no potentiometric studies have been done for the complex formation of trivalent rare earth metal ions with *p*-sulpho-salicylidenesulphanilamide (*p*-SUSASUD). In continuation to our earlier studies^{1,2} on Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes, we report in this paper the formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of trivalent rare earth metal ion complexes of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} with *p*-sulpho-salicylidenesulphanilamide in aqueous medium at different temperatures and ionic strengths.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were either of AR grade or purified before use.

Preparation of the ligand: The ligand, *p*-sulpho-salicylidenesulphanilamide was prepared according to literature³. The purity of the compound was checked by its elemental analysis and melting point determination.

Solution: Double distilled water and carbonate free sodium hydroxide⁴ were prepared. Perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The metal oxides were converted to metal perchlorates and then dissolved in 0.1 *M* perchloric acid solution. Estimation of the metal ions was done by EDTA method⁵.

Apparatus: A digital pH-meter of the Electronics Corporation of India, model 5651 (accuracy ± 0.01 units) with a combined glass electrode assembly was used. All the computations were carried out on an Electronics Corporation of India model EC 62 P programmable calculator.

Bjerrum-Calvin titration: The method of Bjerrum-Calvin^{6,7} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁸ was followed to determine the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants. Following sets of titrations were performed at three different temperatures 32° ($\mu = 0.1$ *M* NaClO₄), 42° ($\mu = 0.1$ *M*, 0.05 *M* and 0.01 *M* NaClO₄), and 52° ($\mu = 0.1$ *M* NaClO₄).

Acid titration : 10 ml 0.1 *M* HClO₄ + NaClO₄ solution + water.

Ligand titration : 10 ml 0.1 *M* HClO₄ + 4 × 10⁻³ *M* ligand + NaClO₄ solution + water.